

The Effects of Analogue Relevance and Prior Analogical Instruction on Problem Solving Ability

Abstract

Analogical transfer is a cognitive process where knowledge from one domain is transferred to another domain to solve a novel problem. Previous research has suggested that use of analogues can potentially enhance problem-solving skills by providing a familiar framework to tackle novel problems. This study investigates the effects of analogue relevance – similarity between a previously-solved problem and a present one – and instruction in the use of analogues on participants’ problem-solving abilities. Participants were recruited to complete ten short sequence-based problem-solving tasks across four experimental conditions, designed to investigate the effects of high-relevance analogues, low-relevance analogues, prior instruction, and a lack of instruction, as well as the interaction effects of the two independent variables. The number of correct answers given by participants was recorded as the dependent variable. Statistical analysis showed a significant main effect of both analogue relevance and prior instruction in analogue use on participants’ problem-solving ability. No significant interaction effects were observed. The findings of the experiment suggest that both higher analogue relevance and receiving prior instruction in analogical problem-solving positively impact problem-solving ability, thereby supporting previous research into analogue relevance and supporting one side of the debate on the value of prior instruction.

Introduction

Problem-solving is a critical skill that enables individuals to navigate complex scenarios and challenges. Research shows that people search for similar circumstances and issues from their long-term memory to inform problem-solving in novel situations (Chen, Mo and Honomichl, 2004, p. 415). ‘Analogical transfer’ is a cognitive process where knowledge from an earlier experience is recalled and used to solve a new, similar problem, which is often considered an essential part of creative thinking (Holyoak and Thagard, 1995, p. 13). The terms ‘analogues’ and ‘analogies,’ in this context, refer to situations or problems that share similar structures or underlying principles. The use of analogues can enhance problem-solving skills by providing a familiar framework to tackle unfamiliar problems, adapting and modifying existing approaches to fit the unique aspects of the current problem. Individuals who engage in analogical reasoning benefit from increased flexibility in their cognitive processes as they are

able to apply knowledge and strategies from one context to another, leading to more effective problem-solving and generalization abilities (Holyoak and Thagard, 1995, p. 53).

It is generally accepted that analogical transfer is an evolved skill, developed in mankind's past to enable us to handle new situations (Holyoak and Thagard, 1995, pp. 1-2). Novelty can imply a danger which needs to be quickly addressed, for which trial and error is simply impossible. To illustrate, an ancient hunter-gatherer would be better served by drawing parallels between a new animal (for example, a cheetah) and one with which they have experience evading (such as a lion) than by attempting to slowly analyze and learn about the new possible threat. Even a less than ideal response, such as running rather than hiding, would likely be better than standing still and simply waiting to be attacked. From there, improvements can be considered, such as relevance and conscious awareness. Would comparing a cheetah to a leopard instead lead to a higher or lower chance of survival? If the hunter-gatherer consciously looks for similarities, would better parallels be drawn, and better solutions identified?

Previous research has suggested that relevance of analogues makes an important contribution to problem-solving, although few studies have been conducted in the area. Raynal, Clément and Sander (2020) investigated the relative importance of surface and structural similarities to analogical retrieval in problem solving, constructing a story-recall task in which life-like scenarios shared structural similarities. They then carried out experiments to test the cognitive plausibility of a structural similarities-based retrieval and found that analogues with structural similarity were more commonly used by participants and lead to better results than analogues with only superficial similarity (Raynal, Clément and Sander, 2020, p. 9). The results of the two experiments showed that the relevance of the analogue is crucial to better performance in problem-solving tasks, and that surface similarity is not enough to promote any significant improvement in problem-solving abilities.

Qualitative research was carried out by Chan, Paletz and Schunn (2012) into problem-solving confidence in uncertain situations, specifically regarding the use of analogies by scientists on the Mars Rover Mission. The researchers analysed transcriptions of informal, task-relevant conversations between scientists on the multidisciplinary Mars Exploration Rover science team (Chan, Paletz and Schunn, 2012, p. 1354). The study found that 'near' or high-relevance analogies were used far more often in discussions than 'far' or low-relevance analogies, suggesting that individuals tend to draw upon experiences and knowledge that

closely align with the current problem when trying to navigate through uncertainty – high-relevance analogues. However, the researchers also noted that ‘far’ analogies, despite being less frequently used, could potentially be beneficial in reducing uncertainty. These analogies, while not directly related to the problem, could provide a different but equally valuable perspective or a novel approach to problem-solving. However, due to the lack of sufficient low-relevance analogue data, the researchers were unable to definitively support or refute this idea (Chan, Paletz and Schunn, 2012, pp. 1365–1366).

A similar study by Catrambone (2002) investigated which aspects of analogues most heavily influence their recall and subsequent use in problem-solving situations. The research findings indicated that the accessibility of information may be primarily influenced by the quantity of overlapping features, whether they are superficial or of a lower-order structural nature, rather than the specific type of overlapping features (Catrambone, 2002, p. 329). However, data from a second experiment implied that the impact of structure is amplified if there is also a similarity in higher-order structure, while the surface effect appeared to be entirely unaffected by structural attributes. It was concluded that lower-order relationships gain advantage from the existence of a unifying, higher-order element which organizes them in a way that consistently triggers a reminder effect that surpasses a certain threshold.

Research into the impact of prior instruction in the use of analogues, while more researched, has been less conclusive, with some researchers arguing that instruction in conscious analogue use improves problem-solving abilities, while others argue that it makes little or even a negative difference. Richland and McDonough (2010) performed a study investigating the critical role of selecting appropriate source analogues in the context of learning new problem-solving techniques, finding that providing learners with explicit comparative cues during the initial teaching phase significantly improves their capacity to identify relevant analogues when faced with new challenges. This was evidenced by experiments in two distinct mathematical scenarios, where the use of comparative gestures and the strategic alignment of source and target problems during the learning process led to a marked increase in the correct application of concepts to new contexts (Richland and McDonough, 2010, pp 38–39).

Tunteler and Resing (2007) carried out research into the impact of prior assistance in using analogies on children’s analogical problem-solving skills over time. The study involved 144 children aged 5 to 7 years from kindergarten and grade 1. Some children were given assistance in using analogies one week before the experiment started, teaching them how to

use analogies to solve problems through a series of exercises and activities designed to familiarize the children with the concept of analogical problem-solving. Their use of analogies over time was then examined and compared with peers who did not receive such assistance, with the results indicating that prior assistance in using analogies has a beneficial effect, which may last for several weeks, on analogical problem-solving in children aged 6-7 years or even younger (Tunteler and Resing, 2007, p. 60). Interestingly, the study found that the children in both conditions were able to draw parallels between the source problem and target problem – even without any instruction or guidance – and attempt a solution ‘because they heard it in the base story,’ suggesting that children of primary school age are capable of identifying similarities and solving problems using analogical transfer without the need for any outside input.

A study into long-term analogical transfer was carried out by Chen, Mo and Honomichl (2004), using American and Chinese folk tales commonly heard by children of those cultures. Participants were each presented with a problem analogous to the folk tale of their own culture, a problem analogous to that of the other culture, and several problems disanalogous to both. The study found that even participants who were not explicitly reminded of the source story heard during their youth – some as distantly as 10 years prior – were found to make use of analogical transfer when solving the target problem, and heavily outperformed participants from the other culture condition (Chen, Mo and Honomichl, 2004, p. 428). This suggested that outright instruction in analogue use is not necessary for successful analogical problem-solving, counter to the aforementioned studies.

Research by Sidney (2020) examined the mathematical learning outcomes of 6th grade children from implicit and explicit analogies during instruction. In the implicit analogy condition, a teacher presented example problems of whole number division and then introduced fraction division without drawing attention to their similarities. In the explicit analogy condition, the teacher introduced the same examples, drew children’s attention to the analogy, and guided children’s through the analogical similarities and how they might use it to solve fractional division problems. Children in the third, no analogy condition were not presented with the whole number division analogy at all. Children who viewed the implicit analogy had far greater conceptual understanding of fraction division than children in the teacher-guided explicit condition or the no analogy condition (Sidney, 2020, p. 11). Children in the explicit condition performed worse on procedural post-test items than both children in the implicit condition and even children who received no analogy at all. The study concluded

that just activating children's prior knowledge of structurally similar problems was more effective at supporting children's learning than explicitly guiding the use of that analogy. This conflicted with previous studies by suggesting that instruction and guided analogy use leads to worse analogical learning and problem-solving outcomes.

It is noteworthy to mention that there has been no previous research investigating the interactions between analogue relevance and instruction in the use of analogues on analogical problem-solving, despite the potential to provide insight into the way in which humans build on prior learning. Considering the already-known benefits of analogical transfer to problem solving, any way to further multiply its effectiveness may provide significant additional benefits to learning and problem-solving.

These previous studies defined very clear gaps in current knowledge, despite the potential value of analogical transfer to real-world problem-solving. Research on the impact of analogical relevance is very sparse and the researchers explicitly state the need for further investigation to come to a solid conclusion. Although there is a greater number of studies on the topic of prior instruction in the use of analogical transfer, their results heavily conflict with one another, necessitating further research to support any side.

The objective of this experimental study was to further investigate the effect of analogues on problem-solving ability. It sought to answer the following question: How does the relevance of analogues and instruction in analogical transfer influence the effectiveness of analogical problem-solving in complex tasks, and how do relevance and prior instruction interact? The hypothesis for the first main effect of this experiment was that the relevance of an analogue will affect participants' problem-solving ability. For the second main effect, the hypothesis was that instruction in the use of analogies in problem solving prior to the analogue presentation and presentation of the problem-solving task will affect participants' problem-solving ability. The hypothesis for the interaction between these two effects was that analogue relevance will have a greater effect on problem-solving ability when a task was attempted after receiving training in the use of analogies in problem-solving than without having received any such instruction.

Method

Design

An independent measures design was used for the experiment, with two independent variables each with two levels. The first independent variable was ‘prior instruction in analogical problem-solving,’ with participants in one condition receiving basic instruction in the use of analogical transfer in problem-solving at the beginning of the experiment while the other did not. The second independent variable was ‘analogical relevance,’ with participants in one condition being given an example problem with a high relevance at the beginning of the experiment, which those in the other were shown a low-relevance example problem. The dependent variable was participants’ problem-solving ability, measured by the number of correct answers given during the experiment out of a maximum total of 10. Participants were randomly allocated to conditions in order to improve validity. The instructions for the tasks and the tasks themselves were standardized, while the order in which the tasks were presented was randomized for each participant. Piloting the study revealed that no changes were necessary.

Participants

A total of 40 individuals participated in the experiment. 21 participants were recruited from the Open University student participant pool via SONA Systems and 19 were recruited from among colleagues of the researcher via email and instant messaging, with no specific criteria required to participate. However, participants with visual impairments or learning difficulties – such as dyslexia – were made aware at the beginning of the study that they may find participation more difficult or uncomfortable than others, but that it would not preclude them from participating. 6 participants indicated a visual impairment or learning difficulty. 15 participants were male (37.5%), and the average participant age was 47.2 years (range = 18-76, SD = 14.21). Sampling was opportunistic, comprising students and colleagues who were available and volunteered to take part. Informed consent was obtained at the beginning of the study via a Gorilla questionnaire, before participants were allowed to access the experiment. No incentive or reward was provided for participating. All participants were naïve to the study.

Materials

The experiment was created and hosted online using Gorilla Experiment Builder (n.d.), while recruitment took place via SONA Systems for student participants. University-supplied open templates for the participant information leaflet, informed consent form, demographics questions and debrief were copied and modified for use in the experiment and have been appended (see Appendix I).

An explanation in the use of analogical transfer for problem-solving was given, using the example of the popular puzzles Sudoku and Kakuro, detailing their similarities and how proficiency in one might carry over to the other. Additionally, two pre-solved example problems were used. One of the example problems – used in the low-relevance analogue condition – was a four-card problem, with cards depicting ‘A,’ ‘B,’ ‘3,’ and ‘4,’ the rule that any double-sided card with a vowel on one side must have an even number on the other, and the question of which pair of cards must be flipped to prove the rule. The second example problem – used in the high-relevance analogue condition – was an object rotation task, containing a sequence of squares and circles rotating 45 degrees and changing colour and three possible answer squares with a question asking which comes next in the sequence. The correct answer to the example was provided in both conditions, as well as an explanation of why the answer was correct. There was no limit to the length of time participants could view the instructions or the analogues – progression to the tasks was controlled by a button labelled ‘Next.’ The instructions and both analogue problems were created by the researcher and have been appended (see Appendix II).

Ten Raven’s Matrix problems were used for the tasks in the experiment, each depicting a 3x3 grid of shapes, with the bottom-right grid square containing a question mark. Beneath the grid was a 3x2 grid of possible answers from which participants could choose each labelled with a letter. Buttons corresponding to the possible answers were presented on the right side of the screen, for participants to submit their answers. Selecting an answer recorded the participant’s answer and advanced the experiment

Figure 1: An example of the tasks.

to the next task. Taking over 2 minutes on a task automatically recorded an incorrect answer and advanced the experiment to the next task. The tasks were created by the researcher and have been appended (see Appendix III).

The experiment was carried out online, and participants took part using their own computers and internet connections. The analysis was carried out using IBM SPSS Version 28 (IBM Corp., 2021).

Procedure

Participants were first split into two groups, with one group receiving a basic explanation and instruction in the use of analogues in problem-solving while the other did not, in order to investigate the prior analogical instruction independent variable. Both groups were then split into two further groups – for a total of four – and presented with one of two pre-solved problems and the steps taken to reach the solution, serving as an analogue. After this, participants in all conditions solved a series of ten problems, which were of high analogical relevance to one of the pre-solved problems and low relevance to the other in order to investigate the analogical relevance independent variable. Each problem had a time limit of two minutes, for a maximum time of twenty minutes plus time spent reading the instructions. Participants then proceeded to the debrief. Screenshots of the Gorilla experiment tree and overview page including all tasks have been appended (see Appendix IV).

Results

The results of the Two-Way Independent ANOVA showed that there was a significant main effect of analogue relevance ($F(1,34) = 4.410$, $p = 0.043$, $\eta^2 = .115$) with high (mean = 6.79; SD = 2.097) and low (mean = 5.21; SD = 2.347) relevance analogues producing significantly different numbers of correctly solved problems. Additionally, there was a significant main effect of prior instruction on scores ($F(1,34) = 4.715$, $p = 0.037$, $\eta^2 = .122$). Participants who received instruction performed significantly better (mean = 6.88, SD = 1.996) at the tasks than those in the no instruction condition (mean = 5.29, SD = 2.390). In addition, no significant interaction was found between the two variables ($F(1,34) = .155$, $p > 0.05$, $\eta^2 = .005$).

The full SPSS Output file has been appended (see Appendix V).

Two anomalous results were omitted from the dataset, due to their low performance compared to the condition average. Upon further investigation, it was found that these

participants spent minimal time reading the instructions and completed the tasks unusually quickly – some in under 5 seconds – indicating a lack of attention. The exclusion of these data points resulted in improved statistical significance for both independent variables.

Discussion

Analogues are valuable, efficient tools for learning and problem-solving, enabling people to complete unfamiliar tasks by drawing parallels to previously solved problems. Little research has been conducted into the area of analogical relevance and its impact on problem solving, though the association is generally seen to be positive based on the few existing studies. Several studies have researched the effects of receiving prior instruction in using analogies, though there is no consensus on whether the effect is positive or negative, prompting further research to obtain more conclusive results. This experimental study sought to further investigate the effect of analogue relevance and instruction in analogical transfer on problem-solving ability, using a pair of example problems of differing relevance and a series of sequence-based problem-solving tasks.

As expected, those participants who were presented with a high-relevance analogue at the beginning of the experiment performed significantly better at the sequence-based problem-solving tasks than those participants who were presented with a low-relevance analogue, regardless of which prior instruction condition the participants were in. This result supports the hypothesis that analogue relevance would have a significant impact on participants'

problem-solving abilities. The findings of the present study support the few existing pieces of research on analogical relevance, which argue that recalling analogues with a higher structural similarity leads to improved problem-solving outcomes than recalling those with lower similarity (Raynal, Clément and Sander, 2020; Chan, Paletz and Schunn, 2012), providing greater insight into a heavily under-researched area.

Participants who received prior instruction were found to perform significantly better than those without, regardless of analogue relevance condition. The findings support the hypothesis that prior instruction in analogue use would have a significant impact on participants' problem-solving abilities. This result aligns with multiple pieces of previous research, which found that instruction in the use of analogues encourages analogical transfer and leads to better problem-solving outcomes (Richland and McDonough, 2010; Tunteler and Resing, 2007). In doing so, it counters research stating that instruction has no (Chen, Mo and Honomichl, 2004) or a negative (Sidney, 2020) impact on problem-solving. As the research of Sidney (2020) was carried out with child participants, however, it is possible that this may be somewhat due to sample differences.

No significant interaction effect was observed between the independent variables, causing a rejection of the hypothesis that prior instruction would exaggerate the impact of analogue relevance.

Very unexpectedly, participants in the low-relevance analogue with instruction condition performed slightly better than those from the high-relevance analogue with no instruction condition and significantly better than those from the low-relevance analogue without instruction condition. This was surprising as the assumption was that being instructed to use a low-relevance analogue to solve a problem would lead to worse results, due to the irrelevance of the analogue to the target problem, while participants who did not receive instruction would be more likely to recognize the lack of similarity between the source and target problems. However, participants who received instruction performed better than participants who did not, regardless of analogue relevance. This has the surprising implication that being able to draw upon any previous experience, regardless of actual similarity to a target problem, improves individuals' problem-solving abilities. This somewhat contradicts previous knowledge, which claimed that overreaching with low-relevance analogues was unhelpful to problem-solving, at least in a mathematical context (Richland and McDonough, 2010, p. 28). Though future research will be needed to verify this result, it suggests that people could

benefit from being taught to draw parallels between their memories of a range of life experiences and knowledge and target problems, as intentionally drawing upon even an irrelevant experience improves problem-solving performance.

The findings of this study have multiple possible implications. Participants who engaged in analogical reasoning demonstrated greater cognitive flexibility, allowing them to apply knowledge and strategies from one context to another effectively, and when made aware of the transfer process, they intentionally sought relevant analogies and applied them to novel situations. It suggests that consciously drawing connections even between seemingly unrelated problems can lead to more creative and effective problem-solving. Individuals who intentionally engage in analogical reasoning may therefore benefit from increased flexibility in their cognitive processes, able to apply knowledge and strategies from one context to another, leading to more effective problem-solving and generalization abilities (Holyoak and Thagard, 1995, p. 53). This has the potential to benefit people in a wide range of fields and industries, as creativity is important to many aspects of life.

Though the circumstance of the study is quite different from the reality of learning in classrooms, the research may also have implications for education. Educators can incorporate analogical thinking into curricula, as encouraging students to explore similarities across subjects and topics can foster creativity and critical thinking, as well as having more direct benefits on certain subjects. In mathematics, for example, students' failure to recognize word problems as comprising known concepts is one of the largest issues faced by educators when teaching algebra in schools (National Mathematics Advisory Panel, 2008, cited in Richland and McDonough, 2010, p. 28). Teachers can explicitly teach analogical reasoning strategies, such as using metaphors, similes, and analogical mapping, to enhance problem-solving abilities. The present study demonstrates that drawing analogies across key similarities is one effective way of leveraging individuals' relevant prior knowledge during new learning when faced with novel problems,

An experimental design is believed to have been the best option for this study, given its nature and intent. Experiments offer a significant advantage over surveys and qualitative methods – namely, the ability to establish causality. This is particularly useful in analogical problem-solving studies, where understanding the impact of specific interventions or strategies – such as analogical relevance or the use of instruction – is crucial. While qualitative methods may be useful to discover the conscious thought processes of participants

using analogues of differing relevance, it cannot produce comparable results nor can it be used to investigate the impact of instruction, as one condition simply lacks instruction. While the use of a survey would allow for a much larger sample size, it faces the same issue of being unable to establish cause and effect.

Future research is needed to either support or disprove the finding that being instructed to use a low-relevance analogue leads to better problem-solving outcomes than not receiving instruction to use a high-relevance analogue and further investigate the implications of such a result. Studies could potentially consider the difference in impact between no, low-relevance and high-relevance analogues on problem-solving, to ascertain whether or not drawing parallels between an irrelevant experience and a current novel problem is better than simply attempting to solve a novel problem blind. If consistently supported, such a finding would greatly impact our understanding of problem-solving and the benefit of individuals seeking out different experiences and knowledge outside of their career industry or main area of academic interest.

One shortcoming of the study is in its sample. Only 40 participants were involved, selected opportunistically rather than randomly, meaning the results' representativeness may be limited. Additionally, the participants were all undergraduates or colleagues of the researcher, further reducing representation and limiting generalizability. However, it is worth noting that the Open University boasts a very diverse range of students in terms of age, cultural background, and life experiences. This diversity could somewhat mitigate the representativeness issue, as the sample might still capture a wide range of participants from several walks of life. Nevertheless, future studies could benefit from a larger, more randomly selected sample to enhance the robustness and generalizability of the findings. Future research in the area of analogical problem-solving could also make use of different, more specific samples, perhaps investigating potential differences in its impact on children, students, adults and the elderly. Chen, Mo and Honomichl (2004, p. 428), for example, stated that high school students showed greater analogical transfer than middle school students. Tunteler and Resing (2007, p. 60) similarly found that 6- and 7-year-old children benefitted more from prior instruction than kindergarten children. The same study also discovered that Chinese college students were more likely to access a source analogue when solving a problem, suggesting a potential cultural difference and possibly resulting in the need for culture-sensitive adjustments to teaching methods, which may prove valuable for future research.

An additional limitation lies in the nature of the tasks used in the experiment. All 10 tasks were Raven's Matrix-style sequence tasks, akin to those commonly found in IQ tests. Raven's Matrices primarily assess abstract reasoning and pattern recognition skills. While these are important components of problem-solving, they do not encompass all aspects of it. Problem-solving also involves skills like planning, decision-making, and adapting strategies, which may not be adequately measured by Raven's Matrices. Though the knowledge generated is valuable to our understanding of these specific types of problem-solving as tested by the tasks, it may not be generalizable to other forms of problem-solving. Additionally, Raven's Matrices may contain cultural bias. The test assumes a certain level of familiarity with the type of abstract reasoning and pattern recognition it requires, the likes of which may not be equally distributed across different cultural backgrounds or socioeconomic groups. Therefore, a possible avenue for further study might involve the use of different source analogues and tasks. The distinct skillsets needed for other task types may interact with analogical transfer in different manners, perhaps responding to instruction or relevance in unexpected ways. Future experimentation, using non-mathematical, non-sequential tasks may, therefore, yield very different results to this and prior research, potentially enhancing our understanding of the process behind analogical problem-solving and the range of domains to which it applies.

The use of analogical transfer can improve individuals' problem-solving skills by providing a familiar basis to tackle unfamiliar problems, building upon existing approaches and solutions to solve the unique aspects of a novel problem. This study sought to investigate how the relevance of analogues and instruction in analogical transfer influence the effectiveness of analogical problem-solving in complex tasks, and how relevance and prior instruction interact. Using a pair of example problems of differing relevance and a series of sequence-based problem-solving tasks, the study found that both exposure to a high-relevance analogue and receiving instruction in the use of analogues in problem-solving improved participants' problem-solving abilities. The findings of the experiment suggest that both higher analogue relevance and receiving prior instruction in analogical problem-solving positively impact problem-solving ability, thereby supporting previous research into analogue relevance and supporting one side of the debate on the value of prior instruction. Interestingly, the results also indicate that guided use of any analogue, whether of high or low similarity to the target problem, leads to improved problem-solving abilities in individuals.

References

- Catrambone, R. (2002) ‘The effects of surface and structural feature matches on the access of story analogs’, *Journal of experimental psychology. Learning, memory, and cognition*, 28(2), pp. 318–334. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037//0278-7393.28.2.318> (Accessed 05 May 2024).
- Chan, J., Paletz, S.B.F. and Schunn, C.D. (2012) ‘Analogy as a strategy for supporting complex problem solving under uncertainty’, *Memory & cognition*, 40(8), pp. 1352–1365. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13421-012-0227-z> (Accessed 04 May 2024).
- Chen, Z., Mo, L. and Honomichl, R. (2004) ‘Having the Memory of an Elephant: Long-Term Retrieval and the Use of Analogues in Problem Solving’, *Journal of experimental psychology. General*, 133(3), pp. 415–433. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-3445.133.3.415> (Accessed 04 May 2024).
- Gorilla Experiment Builder (n.d.) *Gorilla Experiment Builder* [Online]. Available at <https://app.gorilla.sc> (Accessed 07 May 2024).
- Holyoak, K.J., and Thagard, P. (1995) *Mental leaps: analogy in creative thought* [Online], Cambridge, MA; London: MIT Press. Available at <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=8ZRHYv59154C> (Accessed 05 May 2024).
- IBM Corp. (2021) *IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows* (Version 28.0) [Computer Program]. Available at <https://www.ibm.com/spss> (Accessed 07 May 2024).
- Raynal, L., Clément, E., and Sander, E. (2020) ‘Are Superficially Dissimilar Analogs better retrieved than Superficially Similar Disanalogs?’, *Acta Psychologica*, 203, pp. 102989–102989. Available at: <https://doi-org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2019.102989> (Accessed 04 May 2024).
- Richland, L.E. and McDonough, I.M. (2010) ‘Learning by analogy: Discriminating between potential analogs’, *Contemporary educational psychology*, 35(1), pp. 28–43. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2009.09.001> (Accessed 04 May 2024).
- Sidney, P.G. (2020) ‘Children’s learning from implicit analogies during instruction: Evidence from fraction division’, *Cognitive development*, 56, pp. 100956-. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogdev.2020.100956> (Accessed 04 May 2024).
- Tunteler, E. and Resing, W.C.M. (2007) ‘Effects of prior assistance in using analogies on young children’s unprompted analogical problem solving over time: A microgenetic study’,

British journal of educational psychology. Received 17 November 2004; revised version received 22 December 2005, 77(1), pp. 43–68. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709906X96923> (Accessed 04 May 2024).

Appendices

Appendix I

The following are the participant information leaflet, informed consent form, demographics questions and debrief.

Participant Information Leaflet

My name is Govinda Embleton and I am a psychology student at the Open University. As part of my studies, I am conducting a research project that contributes to my degree.

My project explores the effects of similar prior experiences on problem solving. My hope is that the findings will help improve our understanding of learning and problem solving.

The experiment will involve completing ten short problem solving tasks by selecting from a range of multiple-choice answers. A pre-solved problem will be presented beforehand to serve as an example to inform your problem-solving attempts.

The experiment should take about 10 minutes to complete.

Please be aware that participants who suffer from visual impairments or learning difficulties (e.g. dyslexia) may find some elements of the experiment more difficult or uncomfortable than other participants.

Voluntary participation & anonymity

Participation in the study is entirely voluntary. After you have read this information leaflet please feel free to contact me if you have any questions or concerns at govinda.embleton@ou.ac.uk.

For the purposes of carrying out this experiment, the University uses Gorilla with whom the School of Psychology holds an agreement. All information collected within Gorilla will be anonymous - you will not be identifiable to the researcher or in any report resulting from this experiment.

If you decide to take part, you are free to withdraw without having to give a reason and without negative consequences. As the data collected is anonymous, it will not be possible to withdraw from the study once you have uploaded your results as the researcher will not be able to identify you.

How will the data collected in the experiment be used?

Data collected will be aggregated, analysed statistically and summaries of the results will be included in a research report. Before agreeing to take part, please read the Data Protection Privacy Notice below which explains how the data will be managed after collection. If you would like a summary of the findings from the study, please email the researcher govinda.embleton@ou.ac.uk.

Questions, comments or complaints

If at any point you need more information about the study, or you have any concerns, please contact the researcher by emailing govinda.embleton@ou.ac.uk. You can also contact the project supervisor, Dr Helen Sharpe, at helen.sharpe@open.ac.uk. If wish to make a formal complaint, please contact the DE300 module chair at DE300-Chair@open.ac.uk.

How do I give consent to participate?

If you are happy to participate please click the **Next** button at the bottom of this page.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The research study complies with UK and General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) and the UK Data Protection Act 2018. The data collected in this study is anonymous. That means when taking part in this study it is not possible to identify you individually.

The nature of the research is such that you will not be asked to disclose sensitive personal information. The experiment does not require you to disclose special category data (race, ethnic origin, political views, religious affiliation, trade union membership, health issues, or sexual orientation).

How long will the data be used and retained?

All anonymous project data and consent forms will be stored on the researcher's password-protected hard drive, with a backup copy on an encrypted or password protected external drive until the project is completed. Any e-mail correspondence with participants will be destroyed immediately after the data has been collected.

The results of the study will be used as a basis for a research project report as part of the Open University module DE300 Investigating Psychology 3. The author of the study reserves the right to publish the findings as an academic publication, or in another form. Both in the report and any subsequent publication, the anonymous data will be presented in aggregated form.

Will my data be shared with others?

The anonymous project data collected in this study will be available to the researcher, their supervisor and, occasionally, academic staff on the DE300 module team. The project data may also be stored in a secure UK research data archive indefinitely, subject to appropriate legal and ethical practices.

What if I am not happy with how my data has been managed?

If you have concerns about data protection and how your information was handled, please contact the course chair at DE300-Chair@open.ac.uk. You can also contact the OU's Data Protection Team at data.protection@open.ac.uk. If you feel that your concerns about the handling of data have not been resolved, you have a right to lodge a complaint with the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO), who are the relevant regulator for data privacy and protection matters. The ICO can be contacted at Wycliffe House, Water Lane, Wilmslow, 900 047 and your will find more information at <https://ico.org.uk>.

Informed Consent Form

I, the undersigned participant, hereby confirm the following:

Please read the following conditions for participation in the experiment.

- I have read and understood the information set out in the Participant Information Leaflet and the Data Protection Privacy Notice and have had the opportunity to ask questions about the research, the data collection process, and my participation.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the study without giving any reason and without being disadvantaged in any way.
- I understand that once I have completed the experiment, I will not be able to withdraw my data as the experiment is anonymous, and the researcher will not be able to identify my responses.
- I am aged 18 or over.
- I understand that my participation will contribute to psychological research, but I will receive no reward, payment, or other direct benefit.
- I was advised of any risk or disadvantage of participating in this research.
- I understand that the aggregate project data will be used to write a research report for DE300 and any publications which arise from the study.
- I agree for my anonymous data to be stored in a password protected personal computer and encrypted external drive until the project is completed, and may additionally be stored in a secure UK research data archive indefinitely, subject to appropriate legal and ethical practices.

I consent to take part in this experiment.

If you do not wish to give consent to taking part in this experiment, please close your browser now

Next

Thank you for consenting to participate in this research study

Below are several demographic questions. Please answer as honestly as you can.

Please indicate your gender:

What is your age?

18 100

Do you suffer from any visual impairments or learning difficulties (e.g. dyslexia)?

While this will not disqualify you from participating, please be aware that you may find some elements of the experiment more difficult or uncomfortable than other participants.

- Yes
- No

Next

Consent to use your data

If you wish to withdraw your consent now, close your browser now.

I am happy for my data to be included

I would like to express my deepest gratitude for your time and contributions to this research study. Your participation has been invaluable in helping us gain insights and understanding into people's analogical problem-solving abilities and the factors that affect them.

As part of the study, participants were initially divided into two groups. One group were given basic instruction in the use of analogues in problem-solving, while the other wasn't. This was done to test whether conscious awareness and understanding of analogical transfer affected problem solving.

After this, participants were split into two further groups, for a total of four, with each of the two seeing a different example problem. One of these problems was very similar to the problems you later solved while the other example was not similar, in order to observe the impact of analogical relevance – or similarity – on problem-solving.

Once again, I am very grateful for your participation in this study.

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Next

Appendix II

The following are, in order, the guidance for the prior analogical instruction condition, the high-relevance analogue, and the low-relevance analogue.

Analogical transfer is a process where skills learned in one context are used to solve problems in a different but similar context.

The idea is that if two problems share some common features or structure, then the solution to one problem can be transferred and adapted to the other problem.

Next

Sudoku and Kakuro are logic-based number puzzles which share a similar problem structure. They both require the use of elimination techniques to fill in numbers on a grid based on given constraints – importantly, that each digit can only appear once per row and column.

5	3		7			
6		1	9	5		
	9	8			6	
8			6			3
4		8	3			1
7			2			6
	6			2	8	
		4	1	9		5
			8		7	9

However, they also have a major difference. Where every row and column in Sudoku adds up to 45, each row and column in Kakuro has its own sum.

There are enough underlying similarities that, while playing Sudoku will not make one a Kakuro master, the experience can provide a head-start and make learning the other much easier.

Next

This is an example of analogical problem solving.

Example Task

Which box comes next in the sequence?

The answer is the option in the middle, because:

- the rectangle rotates slightly to the right every time;
- the circle and rectangle change which one is in the middle, and;
- they swap colour.

Next

Example Task

You have a set of four cards, each with a number on one side and a letter on the other. The cards are laid out on a table, showing the following faces: A, 3, B, 4. You are told that if a card has a vowel on one side, then it has an even number on the other side. Which two cards do you need to flip over to check if this rule is true?

- A) A and 3
- B) A and 4
- C) B and 4
- D) A and B

The correct answer is: A) A and 3

This is because the rule states that a card with a vowel **MUST** have an even number on the other side. However, it doesn't forbid either even- or odd-numbered cards from having consonants on the other side.

Therefore, cards with vowels (A) must be checked to ensure they do have an even number reverse, and cards with odd numbers (3) must be checked to ensure they don't have a vowel reverse side.

Next

Appendix III

The following are the tasks which were used in the experiment.

Select the letter (A-F) which corresponds to the next box in the sequence:

Select the letter (A-F) which corresponds to the next box in the sequence:

Select the letter (A-F) which corresponds to the next box in the sequence:

A B C

D E F

A	B	C
D	E	F

Select the letter (A-F) which corresponds to the next box in the sequence:

A
 B | C |

D
 E | F |

A	B	C
D	E	F

Select the letter (A-F) which corresponds to the next box in the sequence:

Select the letter (A-F) which corresponds to the next box in the sequence:

Select the letter (A-F) which corresponds to the next box in the sequence:

Select the letter (A-F) which corresponds to the next box in the sequence:

Select the letter (A-F) which corresponds to the next box in the sequence:

A

B

C

D

E

F

Select the letter (A-F) which corresponds to the next box in the sequence:

A

B

C

D

E

F

Appendix IV

The following are screenshots of the Gorilla experiment tree and the overview page containing all tasks.

